

PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF KURASH WRESTLERS FOR COMPETITIONS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the importance of psychological preparation for participation in competitions, the need to use psychodiagnostics to obtain data that would make it possible to predict future achievements and overcome obstacles to achieving the intended result.

Key words: kurash wrestling, psychological preparation, motivation, initial training, individualized training.

Introduction. The psychological preparation of a kurash wrestler for each specific competition begins from the moment he learns about his participation in this competition and ends with the last fight [1, 3, 5]. This entire period of time, no matter how changeable it may be, can be divided into three periods.

The first period is from receiving a message about the upcoming competition to receiving information about the results of the draw.

The second period is from familiarization with the draw to the start of the first bout.

The third period is from the beginning of the first fight until the end of the competition.

These three periods differ, firstly, in the amount and reliability of information received by the athlete, as well as the time limit he has to collect and think through this information in order to prepare for the upcoming competition. Secondly, these periods differ in specific tasks that the wrestler will have to solve during

psychological preparation. Thirdly, means and techniques for solving these problems [2, 4, 6, 7].

The first period of psychological preparation of a kurash wrestler for competition.

The main objectives of the first period are:

- 1) preliminary collection of information about the competition;
- 2) preliminary collection of information about opponents;
- 3) based on the processing of this information, goal setting and determination of general objectives;
- 4) programming means for solving general problems (means of achieving the goal) and setting specific tasks for preparing for the competition;
- 5) practical testing of selected funds;
- 6) maintaining neuropsychic freshness before the start of the competition [8, 11, 12].

Preliminary collection of information about the competition begins with comparing the time of the competition with production, educational or other types of main activities [9, 10, 13]. First of all, the athlete determines how he will be able to prepare for the competition and participate in it without compromising his main activity. Then the wrestler must find out basic information about the competition: the system by which it will be held, the number of penalty points, after collecting which the athlete is eliminated from the competition [11, 14, 15].

Preliminary collection of information about opponents is extremely important. As a rule, a highly qualified, experienced wrestler knows the most powerful opponents in his weight category. The athlete should know which of them will participate in a future competition as early as possible. If an athlete learns that strong wrestlers will participate in the competition, whom he himself has not met on the mat before, he should use a variety of sources of information to learn more about their physical, technical, tactical and volitional characteristics [16, 17].

Goal setting and determination of common tasks are carried out on the basis of processing already received information by comparing one's own capabilities with

the capabilities of perceived opponents. The goal you set may be extremely difficult to achieve. Preparing for a competition and participating in it itself may require great, sometimes extreme, physical, nervous and volitional efforts from the athlete. To mobilize himself for these efforts, the fighter must be well aware of the motives in the name of which he has to act [18].

Programming means for solving general problems and setting specific tasks for preparing for a competition begins after the athlete has made the final decision to achieve a certain goal. Now the wrestler no longer lacks the information he received earlier. He now needs additional information. Where will the competition take place? What is their routine? How will the judging be organized? Which of your comrades will participate in them? Who will go as chairman? Having critically comprehended all this information (it is always not completely complete and not absolutely reliable), the wrestler begins a very important section of psychological preparation - probabilistic forecasting of his future competitive activity, a mental experiment. This is a difficult and responsible moment. The athlete imagines himself in the conditions of the upcoming competition with the greatest possible completeness and clarity. Having conducted a mental experiment, that is, having drawn up a probabilistic program of actions that will lead him to his final competitive goal, the wrestler carefully considers what he should and what he can realistically do in the time remaining before the start of the competition in order to prepare himself for the rational implementation of these actions.

For example, during a mental experiment, he came to the conclusion that he could defeat his main opponent only by attacking without rest throughout the fight. This means that you need to work on your endurance in order to be able to withstand such intense stress yourself. But it is possible to win over another only if you use not standard, but some new or little-known technical means, and the athlete begins to train in this direction.

Practical testing of selected means is absolutely necessary. This check is carried out in practice under conditions that, if possible, simulate the conditions of the future

competition. Basic techniques now need to be trained with full resistance from the partner. Bouts must be held on a mat, the dimensions of which correspond to the size of the mat at competitions, and, as in competitions, not one, but two or three bouts must be held per day, and not only in the evening, but also in the morning and afternoon.

However, when preparing for a competition, the closest attention should be paid to modeling the intended opponents. Sparring partners must be selected so that they are similar in strength, speed, endurance, technical equipment, tactics and strong-willed qualities to future opponents.

Of course, familiarization with the causes and nature of obstacles does not mean that the athlete will be able to foresee all the surprises that he will have to encounter during the competitive struggle. That is why, in the first period of psychological preparation, a wrestler must form a certain positive attitude towards obstacles that may arise in competition, including unexpected ones. He must treat obstacles as conditions in which he can demonstrate his will, his sportsmanship, and gain the right to high self-esteem.

Thus, the main features of the first period of a wrestler's psychological preparation for competition have emerged: the ability to receive a variety of information over a long period of time, repeatedly conduct a mental experiment and test the decisions made in practice, with a view to determining the most likely option for the program of action in the upcoming competition.

Clarification and change of the program of action in the competition occur in connection with the results of the assessment and comprehension of continuously incoming information. For example, an athlete, seeing that by the end of the competition he can receive the same number of penalty points as his opponent, concludes that it is necessary to win cleanly (on a carcass) and as quickly as possible against weak opponents in order to get ahead of his opponent in terms of time spent on winning . On the contrary, having made sure that the opponent will have more

penalty points, the wrestler decides not to take risks and in difficult bouts can plan a draw.

Providing rest between bouts is one of the main tasks of the third period of a wrestler's psychological preparation for competition. A wrestling tournament usually lasts four days. An athlete who reaches the final has 6-7 bouts. On the last day, contractions may occur at short intervals, and their intensity increases. All this can lead to the fact that the athlete arrives at the finals of the competition without a sufficient supply of physical and neuropsychic energy. To prevent this from happening, you need to specially organize rest between contractions. Such rest will be facilitated by: distraction from thoughts about competition; switching to activities not related to competition; autogenic training. All these events involve some isolation of the wrestler.

Conclusions. These are the main provisions of a wrestler's psychological preparation for competition. From the above it is clear that at different periods psychological preparation is closely related either to the technical and physical, or to the theoretical and tactical preparation of the athlete. This is completely natural, and this reveals the special importance of a wrestler's psychological preparation for competition.

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